

THE ROLE OF SOCIAL –SIMULATION GAMES IN DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS OF EFL STUDENTS

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Educating the generation who is able to think critically and creatively is one of the main missions of our Uzbekistan since it allows the youth to tackle problems with confidence, communicate their thoughts and ideas clearly. Enhancing critical thinking in EFL (English as a Foreign Language) classrooms is considered an important factor as it impacts on learner`s ability to learn a language more rapidly and effectively. Furthermore, it brings a lot of enjoyment into learning process resulting students to become more engaged into learning process.

The term critical thinking goes back to 2500 years ago to Socrates who established the significance of asking deep questions that penetrate into thinking before the acceptance of the ideas as a praiseworthy of assurance. Socrates set up the importance of proof seeking, close examination of reasoning and assumptions, analysis of basic concepts determining implications both what is said well and done well. This way of analysis is acknowledged as “ Socratic Questioning” and the best known as critical thinking teaching strategy. In the method of questioning, Socrates highlighted the importance of thinking for precision and logical consistency.(1997). Socratic teaching is not solely teaching itself. It does not involve PPT lectures, thorough lesson plans or mechanical learning. The students are not inactive receivers of knowledge. This type of examination encourages intellectual humility and an enthusiasm to admit unawareness, leading to greater learning and understanding. Furthermore, it furthers evidence-based decision-making and consideration of alternative viewpoints. Hence, the Socratic Method is an essential tool for anyone looking for to develop his critical thinking skills and take on in meaningful communication. Socrates transformed the way we think about education. His questioning techniques promoted a critical approach to learning that continues to have an influence on educational systems.(2003)

In the extensive seminar of The Cabinet of Ministers that was dedicated to the socio-economic development of Uzbekistan The president Shavkat Mirziyayev made one of the important speeches about Critical thinking. Accordingly, every citizen of Uzbekistan must acquire the skills of critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility. All the levels of Educational system must be specialized into upbringing the youth who is able to think critically in all obstacles of life as Mirziyayev mentioned in the Seminar several times. Developing this skill prevents our youth from becoming indifferent, unmotivated and unsophisticated which guarantees that country`s future is in safe hands as our dear President cited. Moreover , he adds that only the youth who is able to think critically can make sensible and fair judgments in any situations and can defend their point of view.

Indeed, in our fast developing world, the country needs the youth who is capable of rebuilding modern society and tackling the issues with coming up creative ideas. The changes that are happening in a Modern Education highly demands applying new approaches which meet these demands. The primary goal of developing critical thinking skills of EFL students is not only educating them, but also enhancing the intellectual ability, which will be highly necessary in their later life. That is, making reasonable decisions, working with different kinds of information, analyzing the situations from different angles can serve as bright examples for this (Shamsiyeva 2023) .So teachers together with parents have high responsibility of communicating with the students more encouraging them to think critically. In accordance with it, several reforms have been initiated in recent years. A bright example of this is The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” introduced on October 8, 2019. In accordance with the Decree, there are huge gaps in the Higher Education system that is the students do not possess the necessary critical and analytical skills. The decree proposes providing Universities and Instiutes with more freedom to allow them to put forward more individualized teaching approach enhance students` creative thinking and motivate learners to be engaged in practice-based education. Moreover, the Decree highlights the importance of designing

higher education academic programs that are actually built up on job market demand and students` interests. (Mirvokhidova 2024)

Indisputably, the higher education system of Uzbekistan has been facing with several positive changes in the recent years. Foundation of international, non-governmental and private universities has given new opportunities in the sphere of education. Presently, there are 224 functioning higher educational institutions in Uzbekistan in total. (Mirvokhidova 2024). As a result, the field has been seeing reasonably fair contest among universities to propose excellent education. Particularly, teaching English at universities as a foreign language has witnessed notable changes. Communication based and learner centered approaches of methodologies replaced traditional ways of teaching that were based on memorizing grammar, drilling and repetition

Foreign educators and researchers J.Braus and d.Vund define the term critical thinking as a sensible way of thinking that is based what to rely on and what to do. As they cited it is highest point of intelligence that is thinking sensibly and logically. The technology of critical thinking appeared in the USA in the 1980s and came into Russia in 1990s. Therefore, critical thinking is not a talent, but it is set up skills and abilities that are developed throughout years. It dramatically widens person`s horizon. By thinking critically, a student realizes the very root of any social and environmental issue. Critical thinking enables a person to become successful, happy, and rich and well- respected. By thinking critically one is able analyze core root of the issue, and make judgments about possible consequences of it. A student is able to think critically can take advantage of the evidence wisely, express his opinion precisely, differentiate the fake information from true one, and keep patient if there is not enough evidence to make a decision. (Soros 2004)

Critical thinking skills are crucial in our speedily changing world. Our Uzbekistan needs the youth who can evaluate information, judge the evidence and make sophisticated decisions. Yet, conventional way of teaching does not always supply the best atmosphere for enhancing these skills. And this is where social-simulation games come useful. The games enable students provide an alluring learning experience that

involves participants, facilitate them to try out with diverse scenarios, and assists them develop critical thinking skills. The study which was carried on by Research and Markets informed that the application of social - simulation games in education is growing.(2023) In accordance with Dr John Smith such games offer a unique opportunity for students to enhance the critical thinking skills in a harmless and controlled environment. By performing decision-making and problem-solving in a simulated environment, students can learn from their mistakes and improve their decision-making skills over time. (2023). One of the key advantages of simulation games is that they provide students with real-world experience where they are put into an imitated environment and are allowed to make decisions and see the outcomes of their decisions. This gives them a chance to apply a precious learning knowledge into real-world situations. In a study conducted by the University of Colorado (2023), students who took part in a simulation game were found to possess higher critical thinking scores than those who did not take part.

Moreover, Social- simulation games have sprung up as an influential instrument for hypnotic learning. They put forward an efficient and interactive atmosphere where students can conduct experiment with various scenarios and upshots that can be quite impossible to reach in conventional classroom atmosphere. According to Traci Sitzmann , the hypnotic nature of model games develops learning by enabling students to enhance critical thinking skills throughout practical experience. Together with providing a hypnotic learning experience, simulation games are also modeled to be appealing and enjoyable. Being based on interaction and completion, simulation games inspire students to devote more time and effort into learning, guiding to higher levels of recollection and remembering. A case by Traci Sitzmann (2011), a professor of management at the University of Colorado, discovered that students who learned all the way through social- simulation games had a 20% higher rate of recollection and remembering than those who learned through conventional classroom approaches. The enjoyment feature of social- simulation games can also guide to grown motivation and eagerness for learning, which has a positive effect on general outcome.

In addition, Social- simulation games are planned to provide a safe environment for students to learn and be improved. Differing from real-world decision-making, where mistakes can have considerable cost, students in social-simulation games have a chance of trying out without fear of failure.

This risk-free environment enables them to discover various strategies, methods and viewpoints to problem solving, and learn from their mistakes without any harmful effect on the real world. Also, by encouraging experimentation and learning, these games also empower students to increase confidence in their decision-making abilities. This is because they are able to experiment various scenarios and see the consequences of their decisions, which enables them feel more contented and competent during decision-making process in the real life.

As a result, social- simulation games can become a dominant implementation for building up skills and competencies that are crucial in EFL classes.

There are an increasing numbers of researches on the efficiency of social-simulation games for enhancing critical thinking skills. A study by Van Eck (2006) discovered that these games are mainly effectual for learning complex notions.

In conclusion, social -simulation games are becoming progressively more acknowledged as a way to provide hypnotic learning experiences for students. It also inspires learners to be deeply involved with the content, concerning logic and reasoning to rise above challenges

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